

A Study of Managerial Analysis of Management Education Institutes

Dr. Kamaljeet Kaur Bhatia

Principal, Radiant Institute of Management & Science Indore (M.P.)

Corresponding author- **Dr. Kamaljeet Kaur Bhatia**

Email:-kbhatiavitm@gmail.com

Abstract

Institutions of higher learning face a new situation on higher education. The article studies special aspects of managerial analysis of management education institutes through the use of correlation analysis. There were two management institutes of Indore city. Chi square test were used. The study looks at the problems in management education with a managerial emphasis. The researcher has suggested an entirely new perspective of the Shared Vision Concept wherein the objectives of all the three stakeholders, students, industry and academia are met and the net result is the production of quality, industry ready students to meet the needs of the industry. Also, the academia would be benefitted by increase in number of students and introduction of new courses. The paper also identifies some serious challenges facing education managers in order to achieve educational goals.

Keywords: - Managerial Skills, Management Education Institutes.

Introduction: -

Education, being part of the service industry, is characterized differently from the manufacturing industry, as its product, i.e. knowledge, is intangible. Effective education relies much on its personnel's knowledge, experience, and ethics. Supply chains are relatively easy to define for manufacturing industries, where each participant in the chain receives inputs from a set of suppliers, processes those inputs, and delivers them to a different set of customers. Management is all about improving the organizational performance and involves the management functions of planning, organizing, staffing, leading and controlling. Management practices ensure the best possible educational outcomes through the integration of different resources of schools and colleges. Today, management experts continue to trumpet the idea that human resources are the most important asset of the organization. They make a difference in the success and failure of the organization.

Concept of Management Education:

As a stream of education and training, management education has acquired new dimensions in the modern economic scenario all over the world. Management methodologies is an exciting tool, if implemented well it can have an immediate impact on the operations of any business. The dynamic in nature of Management field allows it to continuously introduce new tools and techniques to improve the efficiency, productivity, and profitability of any organization. Management methodologies are used by all organizations and their departments, functions, and groups. These methods include problem solving techniques, efficient and effective process building guidelines for developing suitable strategies; leading to goal achievement.

Importance of Management Education:

Management education seems to have following aims:

1. Increase the understanding of the factors which influence the conduct of Organizations.
2. Provide students with the tools and techniques that they may use to influence organizational life.
3. Influence the economy in general.
4. Develop overall functional knowledge of a business organization through general management.
5. Acquire in-depth knowledge of minimum one discipline of Management.
6. Enhance the ability to adapt to new environments at micro- and macro- levels.
7. Improve problem detecting, analysing and solving ability.

Review of Literature: -

Alma Acevedo, University of Puerto Rico, USA (2011) in "Business ethics 101: The student is not a customer". The current trend is to treat students as customers. This has been done to study the impact of market values on university based business education. In any market based study, it is necessary to observe and study the reactions of customers in order to understand the effectiveness of market. The article pointed out the ethical implications of this focus. Role of language and language games was also pointed out. The author expressed a view that there is a flaw in the understanding students as customers because this is very much there in the academic culture and these are implied ethics part of the academic culture. This needs to be effectively implemented and practised.

John T. E. Richardson (2009), The Open University, in their write up on **Face-toface versus online tutoring support in business studies courses in distance education**. The distance learning course students were given an opportunity to undergo some course work through conventional face to face method of teaching and learning. Their experiences were compiled by contacting them through telephonic interviews or through email questionnaire. It has been observed that these students rate their tuition fee favourable when it is

divided online rather than face to face. The students who sought online tuition rated their workload as more appropriate. Their perceptions of the quality of their academic courses and the approaches to study that course were concerned had notice no significant difference. Introduction of online forms of tutorials depends on the appropriate training and support to the tutors and students. There were no significant differences between the students who received face to face tuition against those who received online tuition. **Alan Reeves (2008), University of the West of Scotland, and Russell Rimmer, Queen Margaret in their commentary on “Explaining performance in an Executive MBA”.** To attract new entrants to MBA and executive MBA programmes it is necessary to predict student success. The data from University of Paisley has been used to predict this behaviour. Use of rational choice theory and students integration model in combination with critiques of student learning was done for the purpose of the study. The information collected from the students’ admission forms revealed that they want to register for the courses to ingrate academically, social integration, social networking, career progression and obtaining an advanced degree qualification. The students who joined the course with an intention to have academic integration performed better compared to others. Their graduate GPAs were higher than others. Those who joined the course with an intention to have social networking were poor performers and they got very low GPAs compared to others. Similarly the effect of work experience on the performance of the students was also measured. To measure this relation the synthesized model was used. It was observed that the breadth of experience and the sector in which the experience was gained played an important role in the performance of the students. It also played an important role when these students interacted with the employers from other sectors. The purpose of the paper was to initiate further research on the connection between graduate GPA, jobs held and roles performed, tasks exercised and competencies acquired.

Objectives of the Study:-

Analysis and Interpretation:-

1. To evaluate the existing system of management and business education.
2. To analyse the impact of student development activities conducted by management institute.
3. To analyse the various functional aspects related with business educations.

Hypotheses Of The Study:-

H01:- Corporates prefer candidates with work experience for their campus placements.

H02:- Corporates show no preference in choosing candidates from the institutes which gives exposure to student with career development activities.

H03:- Corporates reveal no preference in choosing candidates based on their summer internship experience and quality of internship that candidate had been through.

Methodlogy:-

The data required for the study were collected from Primary and secondary sources of information. Primary data were collected using questionnaires and through formal and informal discussions with the concerned members. To analyse the data collected Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.0 were employed for the present study.

Sample and Sample Size:-

Management students who had enrolled and completed management education at post graduate level between the periods 20017-2022 at two tier Business Schools in Indore. Convenient random sampling is being used for selection of respondents. Total 80 respondents were surveyed in Indore city.

Statistical Tool:-

The purpose of the study was to examine the student and industry expectations of management education. Therefore, two separate questionnaires were designed for the two set of respondents.

1. Students’ Questionnaire:- The questionnaire administered to the students was designed to elicit information.

2. Company Questionnaire:- The Company questionnaire had questions on the Company size as measured by the number of employees, listing status, location, policy on campus recruitment, hiring of fresher’s, preferential institutes for hiring, weightage to academic and other achievements.

Table 5.26

Experience candidate preference	Observed Frequency (Fo)	Expected Frequency (Fe)	Chi-square (χ^2)
Yes	23	40	7.225
No	57	40	
Total	80		

The calculated Chi square value is 7.225. The table value at 1 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 3.841. Since the calculated value is greater than the table value at 5% level of

significance it can be concluded that critical value the preference corporates of opting for no experience is significant. So we reject null hypothesis (**H01**).

Table 5.29

Candidates with exposure to career development activities preferred	Observed Frequency (Fo)	Expected Frequency (Fe)	Chi-square (χ^2)
Yes	65	40	31.250
No	15	40	
Total	80		

The calculated Chi square value is 31.250. The table value at 1 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 3.841. Since the calculated value is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance it can be concluded that critical value

the preference of corporates opting for candidates with exposure to career development activities is significant. So we reject null hypothesis (**H02**).

Table 5.21

Summer internship experience and its quality preference	Observed Frequency (Fo)	Expected Frequency (Fe)	Chi-square (χ^2)
Yes	69	40	42.050
No	11	40	
Total	80		

The calculated Chi square value is 42.050. The table value at 1 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 3.841. Since the calculated value is greater than the table value at 5% level of significance it can be concluded that critical value the preference corporates of opting quality summer internship experience candidates is significant. So we reject null hypothesis (**H03**).

Findings:-

1. Big Companies in terms of size (measured by the number of employees) prefer to recruit from Grade A Institutes as they are of the opinion

that these candidates are a better fit in the corporate world.

2. It has been observed that listed companies are the main recruiters of students of Grade A and Grade B Institutes.
3. The Companies laid a lot of emphasis on the right attitude of students which scored above skills such as communication and leadership. These skills may be acquired by the students with some inputs whereas good attitude has to be a part of the psyche of the student.
4. It was observed that summer internships play a vital role in giving the students some limited

exposure to corporate working. The company respondents also felt that summer internships should form an integral part of the MBA curriculum.

Limitations of the Study:-

1. Faculty related issues are not covered in the study since AICTE has specified guidelines on the qualification and faculty-student ratio.
2. Curriculum related issues are not covered for university affiliated courses, since all of them have to follow a common curriculum. For PG courses due to confidentiality and competitiveness, Institutes are reluctant to share curriculum information.
3. This study is restricted to the Management Institutes operating in the city of Mumbai. Obviously the observations and results may vary in other locations.

Conclusion:-

1. Evaluation of the existing system of management and business education:-
2. India is the largest provider of global talent and in recent years there have been massive structural and systemic changes in the higher education system that is slowly starting to yield results. The existing system of management and business education, with a few notable exceptions continues to be out dated and academic in nature. Institutes have been unable to adapt to the changing needs of various sectors of the industry and services.
3. It has been seen that there is a significant correlation between the rise of management education and industrial and economic development.
4. There is a general consensus among the industry experts and academicians that there will be a steep increase in demand for postgraduates in management in the coming years.
5. Though the number of business schools has trebled in the last decade, the quality of education leaves much to be desired.

Recommendations:-

1. **Attracting the best talent:** Management education in India is plagued by the problem of shortage of quality faculty. The problem lies not in 'quality' faculty as measured by the degrees earned but quality faculty that is relevant to industry need and can engage with the students for learning effectiveness. In order to attract faculty with corporate exposure, the researcher recommends putting in place mechanisms for performance based appraisals and incentives.
2. **Incentives to Promote Research:** Realising the importance of research, it is necessary to motivate faculty for research for this purpose. The incentive can be in the form of relaxation in teaching workload, relieving them from certain

administrative responsibilities and also providing library facility with physical and on-line journals, databases, etc. Management institutes should inculcate proper motivation and interest among faculty for research. This can be done by providing incentives to faculty involved in research, giving due weightage to research activities and providing a good library support system. A paradigm shift in how management education is viewed will happen if the focus is shifted to promoting research capabilities among faculty, writing case studies based on Indian companies.

3. **Faculty Evaluation:** A good faculty evaluation and management system, an effective student feedback system would also play an important role in attracting the best talent from the industry. These parameters would present a clearer picture of the quality of management education being imparted.
4. **Industry-Faculty Interaction:** To encourage interaction of faculty with industry and the executives, it is recommended that the industry experts can be appointed as part-time or full-time faculty or if possible giving them adjunct faculty position in the institutes. Faculty interaction with executives should be enhanced by increasing participation of industry experts in academics either by appointing them as full time faculty or part time faculty.

References: -

1. **Alma Acevedo, (January 2011)**, Business ethics 101: The student is not a customer.
2. **Habib, Dr. Md. Mamun. (2010)**. "Supply Chain Management for Academia, LAP Lambert Academic Publishing, Germany, ISBN 978-3-8433-8026-3
3. **Zikmund, W.G. (2010)**, Business Research Methods, 7th Edition, Thomson South-Western.
4. **John T. E. Richardson August (2009)**, Face-to-face versus online tutoring support in business studies courses in distance education.
5. **Priya, A.(2007)**"Global World & Quality of Management Education in India", available At : http://www.indianmba.com/faculty_column/fc631/fc631.html (accessed on 18 Sep,2012)
6. **Alan Reeves(2008)**, University of the West of Scotland, and Russell Rimmer, Queen Margaret in their commentary on "Explaining performance in an Executive MBA".